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DRX381451: YK686

1 ILLUMINA (Illumina MiSeq) run: 68,340 spots, 18.4M bases, 6.2Mb downloads

Submitted by: KYOTO_CER**Study:** Coevolution of ectomycorrhizal fungi and angiosperm at the late Cretaceous drives host-fungus co-diversification[PRJDB13910](#) • [DRP011432](#) • [All experiments](#) • [All runs](#)[show Abstract](#)**Sample:** YK686[SAMD00515458](#) • [DRS373763](#) • [All experiments](#) • [All runs](#)*Organism:* [Pseudocolus schellenbergiae](#)**Library:***Instrument:* Illumina MiSeq*Strategy:* AMPLICON*Source:* GENOMIC*Selection:* PCR*Layout:* PAIRED*Construction protocol:***Spot descriptor:**

1	forward	137	reverse
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Runs: 1 run, 68,340 spots, 18.4M bases, [6.2Mb](#)

Run	# of Spots	# of Bases	Size	Published
DRR395672	68,340	18.4M	6.2Mb	2024-04-08

ID: 32500426